

Policy Brief

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Towards the Computational Modelling of Human Migration Using Agent-based Simulations

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Key Points

- Social simulations via agent-based modeling that study the phenomenon of migration allow for a bottom-up approach, through which individual behavior is analyzed at a micro level and its impact on global dynamics is represented at a macro level.
- Contemporary agent-based approaches cover various topics within migration research, such as agent and environmental behavior, computational scalability, health factors, political conflicts, or human trafficking and slavery.
- Besides technical challenges in developing agent-based models, their usage for policy also faces impediments due to implicit assumptions, uncontrolled spread of models, limited transferability, or open interpretability of results.
- In conjunction with agent-based models, the combination of semantics and ontologies can tackle these impediments by explicitly modeling underlying assumptions, the semantic and contextual embedding of the development process, and the provision of transparency and reproducibility of the model and the construction of the simulation.
- The employment of agent-based models also impacts complementary policy topics by demanding actions in the area of data spaces, training and capacity building for new technologies, and national AI strategy guidelines for the migration context.

Background

One of the grand challenges of modern societies is represented by the necessity to understand their underlying complex social behaviors and phenomena, one of them being migration. Since migration is a transitional process, it impacts all involved states, regardless of whether they are the origin, the destination, or transition state. Migration impacts numerous aspects of the social lives, ranging from the demographic changes that arise as a consequence of it, all the way to the fusions of cultures to economic effects, e.g., on the labor market or political systems (Hinsch & Bijak, 2022). The latter often struggle to deal with the phenomenon of migration in terms of national economics and security, as well as with the diplomatic negotiations between unions of states, such as the EU. This struggle expresses itself via policies that do not necessarily result in the anticipated effect concerning the governance of migration (Triandafyllidou, 2022). In order to overcome these problems, evidence-based policymaking aims to refine those policies in order to increase their impact and sustainability (Baldwin-Edwards et al., 2019).

One way of implementing evidence-based policymaking in the domain of migration is via the use of agent-based models (ABMs). These social models consist of a simulated population constructed of individual agents, and in the simulated world these agents can act autonomously and interact with each other and their environment. Each (type) of agent holds its agenda,

attributes (e.g., sex, age, income, education), as well as some rule-based restrictions and behaviors (McAlpine et al., 2021). The simulation tries to mimic the real world as closely as possible to deduct dynamics and outcomes that would realistically reflect the impacts of implemented policies (Wilensky & Rand, 2015).

In the remainder of this policy brief, current state-of-the-art applications of ABMs in migration are presented, followed by an analysis of the challenges concerning their implementation. Against this backdrop, a novel approach to reducing these hurdles is presented. Concluding this policy brief, three concrete policy implications are presented that concern the implementation of ABMs in evidence-based policymaking within the context of migration policies.

Application areas of ABMs within the migration context

The body of literature concerning the application of agent-based models within migration research has significantly risen in recent years. In the following, an overview of contemporary application areas is provided based on the literature review conducted by De Luca et al. (2022).

One emerging topic is the investigation of correspondences between the rules of individuals and the rules of the model society in which the individuals reside. M'hamdi et al. (2019) study the problem of dual or parallel evolution in artificial societies to model the separate evolutionary dynamic and the eventual convergence of Eastern and Western countries. The agent, in their model, migrates according to a decision function that considers both the availability of resources (and thus, the economy) and the level of repression that they suffer (and therefore, politics); their study concludes that, if a society is experiencing a crisis, the emigration of some of its components may help it survive and continue evolving, whereas in the absence of emigration that society is more likely to perish.

Another interesting topic is presented by the modeling of migration policies via agent-based models. Simon et al. (2018) address the question of changes in the behavior of a migrant as a response to changes in the immigration policies that affect them personally. Specifically, the authors study the transition of a migrant from preferring a legal migration pathway to preferring irregular migration instead; this transition occurs in response to the tightening of immigration policies. The use case they consider for model calibration consists of the various classes of voluntary migration from Jamaica, primarily comprising students and laborers. Their main finding is that migration behavior, and in particular the choice by an individual to not migrate as opposed to migrating, is largely insensitive to policies: only in cases where enforcement is very strong does the decision to migrate change into non-migration. In all other cases, where enforcement of restrictions is lax, the migratory behavior is unaffected, but the migrants end up classified by the legal system of the hosting country as “irregular” rather than “regular”.

Concerning the relationship between the moving human and the environment around them, Nelson et al. (2020) discuss the nomadic behavior of shepherds in Somalia and how the civil war and the ecological environment interact with them. The authors integrate geospatial data into an agent-based model and simulate the process by which a nomadic pastor may decide to move between areas to feed their livestock. If unable to do so, and particularly in case of death

of the livestock due to undernutrition, the nomadic pastor may transition to become an internally displaced person, which is eventually picked up in the corresponding statistics. The authors' model finds a strong relationship between the access to vegetation by pastors and their permanence in that role; however, it remains unclear about the nature of the existing relationship between conflicts and the generation of internally displaced persons: this article reinforces the idea of an existing connection between economic hardships (and not necessarily the conflict alone) and the generation of internally displaced persons, which has also been noted in countries other than Somalia (Yigzaw and Abitew, 2019).

Moving on to the next complex, health and genetic factors that affect migration and the differences between families and households in migration models were also investigated. Kishore et al. (2021) relate to the impact on human mobility caused by the lockdowns adopted in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. The authors of this study show that shortly after the lockdown had been approved, a significant increase in mobility was observed before it entered into force. Contrary to expectations, the adoption of lockdown measures that aimed to decreasing mobility in the long term and thus preventing diffusion of pathogens may rather cause an increase in diffusion in the short term, and a spread to areas that would otherwise not be reached in the absence of lockdown measures. The relevance of this study for the broader discipline of migration studies consists in the consideration that individuals react not only to mobility policies that are enforced, but also to mobility policies that have been approved but not yet applied.

Concerning the theme of conflicts and war and the impact that these have on the movement of refugees, Suleimenova et al. (2021) discuss a methodology for developing ABMs incrementally and via the iterated usage of sensitivity analysis (Sobol 2001). The authors validate the choice of parameters for their model on the figures by UNHCR on the arrival of refugees to refugee camps in Mali, Burundi, South Sudan, and the Central African Republic. Upon an initial choice of parameters that describe the motion of a moving refugee, they apply sensitivity analysis to determine which ones are more pivotal to predicting the model's validation dataset; they then update the most influential parameters according to some rules and then repeat the process of sensitivity analysis and validation of the model. The argument that they propose is that, by iterating this procedure a sufficient number of times, the model would converge to a parametric configuration that would correspond to some measure of optimality; however, this hypothesized convergence remains unproven and may correspond to a local rather than the global optimum.

The last topic to discuss here concerns the optimization and scalability challenges that ABMs are facing in terms of representing the dynamics of large groups of people. Here, one example is given by Makarov et al. (2018), who discuss a methodology for developing large-scale agent-based simulations that include agents in the order of one billion, which is intended to replicate one-to-one the evolution of social systems in Eurasia. The model was used to simulate economic migration from China to Russia and was capable to represent the flow of information between agents. In its application to the regional migration between the Chinese province of Heilongjiang and the Far East Federal District in Russia, the authors claim that the model can

accurately represent the changes in the flow of labor migrants across the border in response to changes in the bilateral currency exchanges and the availability of job offers.

Key findings

Based on the analysis of the before-discussed application areas, several challenges could be identified when using agent-based modeling within migration policymaking. A subset of the most challenging aspects is presented in line with the current literature on that topic (e.g., Edmonds, 2018).

Challenges towards the use of agent-based simulations in migration research

Implicit assumptions. One of the grand challenges of any simulation, be it agent-based approaches or other attempts, comes from the underlying complexity of the phenomenon to capture in a particular environment, and from the necessity to incorporate the respective actors. This leads to the need to reduce complexity by introducing constraints to the model, and this subsequently increases the level of fuzziness of results, biases, and underlying suppositions. This process takes place at both the individual level, as well as at a cultural and institutional level. The increase in the biases and underlying assumptions may then lead to the introduction of intangible influences that do not necessarily reflect reality. These influences can relate to, e.g., the use of yet-to-be-proven theories, arguments between schools of thought such as structure versus human agency, or econometric aspects such as the usage and usefulness of neoclassical economic models. To address this challenge it is necessary to explicitly state and express all underlying assumptions that have found their way into the model, even when they seem trivial from the perspective of migration studies but might not be so for other disciplines.

Uncontrolled spread. The purpose of creating a model is the possibility to reuse and distribute it without the necessity to repeat the time-consuming process of constructing the model from scratch. Also, by distributing the model, experts can get easier access to it, enabling them to analyze and evaluate the model. However, once a model has received a critical level of acceptance within the domain and its community, it is often reused without further questioning. Considering this circumstance from the policy perspective, this can have severe implications for decision-makers that may be tempted to act upon the results based on an erroneous or outdated model; as research progresses, the new insights that derive from it may have not yet found their way into the established model. Hence, it is crucial to accompany agent-based models with a thorough, continuous review and testing cycle, including sensitivity analysis due to the rapidly changing (socio-political) environment that might impact the underlying assumption within the model.

Limited transferability. When developed, models target a particular use case in the form of a specific geographic region, population, dataset, time, or phenomenon under observation; hence, they are highly specific. This also implies that, by transferring the model into another context and thus changing core variables and conditions, applicability and interpretability of the model itself might vary. It is, therefore, vital to understand the model's background and the

specific purpose that the modelers had in mind during its development. While it might be tempting to shift to a “generalized model” or to use existing models in other contexts or domains that are deemed to be “somewhat similar”, this should be avoided, even if as a consequence the modelers would require larger resources and longer time to build a new one from scratch.

Open interpretability. Models are developed to simulate certain events, improve understanding of phenomena of interest, or analyze forecast scenarios based on different strategical options. These applications have one thing in common; i.e., that their results and underlying evidence are always open to different interpretations. While different interpretations can lead to a valuable and essential debate concerning the adoption of respective policy options, there is uncertainty introduced by the lack of transparency on the reasons why the analysis of the results of a model may have led to specific interpretations. This can, in turn, lead to a false sense of security by expert systems removing responsibility for decision-making processes. Furthermore, the presence of underlying implicit assumptions that, as discussed above, are certainly present in any given model, might lead to the reaffirmation of a particular worldview. Additionally, it could also lead to the reinforcement of self-fulfilling prophecies, and prevent the consideration and adoption of alternative strategies and associated actions. In addition, the pure reliance on factual analysis might also lead to a reduction of reflection on social and ethical values, which are of utmost importance for cohesive societies.

Combining semantics and ontologies to support the creation of ABMs

As outlined before, using agent-based models in migration research is challenging. While no “one-size-fits-all” solution is available, several challenges can be addressed by using a combination of semantics and ontologies while modeling and testing agent-based simulations. In particular, this combination can successfully address i) the challenge of proper contextual embedding by semantic analysis of supporting policy documents and other data sources; ii) the explicit modeling of underlying concepts, relationships, and definitions via ontologies; iii) the use of semantic web approaches and knowledge graphs to link data and policy documents to modeled concepts and relationship for increased transparency; iv) the support of model developers in constructing base-line models to be further refined via a transparent and reproducible approach, interlinking state-of-the-art agent-based modeling software and the ontology-based knowledge bases. The abstract process can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Abstract process flow of a semantical and ontology-based classification workflow for ABM development

In the first step (1), domain experts define the concepts and their definitions, including their relationships, and integrate them into an ontology. These concepts can be actors within the agent-based model, such as different forms of migrants, environmental objects, or specific events. As the ontology needs to be machine-interpretable, formal description languages such as the Ontology Web Language (OWL) (Hitzler et al., 2009) can be used for this purpose. Besides the definition of the concepts, associated computational values, thresholds, and programming artifacts necessary for building the model and integrating it into the simulation can also be linked. If necessary (2), further background information and relevant datasets can be included by linking them from the semantic web using OWL-compatible languages such as the Resource Description Framework (RDF) (Manola, et al., 2004). Matching the definitions provided in the knowledge base, the experts also store the required simulation artifacts within a database and link them back to the ontology for future reference (3).

When a model and upon that a simulation are being created, the process of development can be started by providing relevant documents (4); these are, for example: policy documents, reports from the region of interest, news items, or social media posts. Via a semantic analysis, e.g., by using a state-of-the-art transformer-based approach such as BERT (Ma et al., 2021), topics and sub-aspects of these topics can be extracted. These topics and aspects can then be searched (5) within the knowledge base, i.e., the ontology. Once found, the attached information, data, and programming artifacts can be gathered (6) and passed to ABM programming environments such as GAMA (Grignard et al., 2013). From there, the developer can further refine the simulation and test additional modifications to the existing data, knowledge, and components of the simulation (7). After an evaluation (8), the experts can reflect on the results, and the necessary updates and new insights can be transferred back into the knowledge base.

Policy Implications

Existing research and the body of literature have demonstrated how versatile agent-based models can be in their application and the high degree of complexity they can reassemble in the context of policymaking. Especially concerning the topic of migration and the different social and political approaches linked to it, the use of ABMs opens up many opportunities while

at the same time increasing challenges for decision-makers. This policy brief, therefore, outlines the following impacts and recommendations in the relevant policy areas due to the use of ABMs in the migration context.

POLICY IMPACT 1 – Data Space for Security and Law Enforcement

Data availability is of great importance when it comes to agent-based models, as otherwise, modeling and testing of models become difficult to impossible beyond pure theory-based approaches. One way of increasing data availability, especially from a cross-border point of view, is the creation of so-called data spaces. Currently, the European Commission is pushing the development of such data spaces in various domains¹, also within security and law enforcement, to combat crime, enhance border security and facilitate legal migration. While the referred Horizon Europe call² targets artificial intelligence as its core aspect in this data space, the same underlying requirements are also valid for agent-based models. By actively participating and collaborating, national and European law enforcement authorities can develop joint quality standards at the EU level.

POLICY IMPACT 2 – Training and Capacity Building

Training and capacity building around technologies such as agent-based models within policy education is important. Following the suggestion of ICMPD's migration policy cycle³, computer-based modeling tools such as ABMs are an innovative approach within the policy design phase. Training simulations in tertiary education programs concerning the simulation of migration-related policy negotiations have already been developed.⁴ The addition of ABMs could improve and extend such educational gamification approaches further. In addition, the extension of existing policy-related training and university programs will primarily benefit from adapting computational social science approaches (Kuchler & Stroebel, 2022), including agent-based models.

POLICY IMPACT 3 – Artificial Intelligence Strategies to Foster ABM in Migration

There exist several approaches how to introduce behavior into agent-based models. One way of achieving this is by using artificial intelligence (AI) to reflect the learned behavior of individuals and environments. Hence, policymakers need to foresee national strategies to engage with AI and migration. During the development of the EU AI Act⁵, all Member States have already developed their national approach, including Austria⁶. While a principal commitment to a human-centric approach and ethical embedding of AI is targeted, the domain of migration and national security within the Austrian strategy is not mentioned. Hence, it is crucial to establish dedicated boundaries and guidelines concerning the use of AI within the migration domain, including profiling, asylum and border control contexts, as well as

¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52020DC0066>

² <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/digital-2022-cloud-ai-02-sec-law>

³ <https://www.icmpd.org/news/the-migration-policy-cycle-making-the-case-for-evidence-informed-and-inclusive-policy-making>

⁴ https://www.eeas.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/SIM1-European%20Council%20simulation_Migration.pdf

⁵ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52021PC0206>

⁶ https://www.bmvit.gv.at/dam/bmvitgvat/content/themen/innovation/publikationen/forschungspolitik/ki-strategie_bundesregierung/AIM_AT_2030_UA.pdf

prediction and risk assessment, which are all relevant applications for agent-based simulations.

Further Reading/References

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